

ANALYSIS OF 3D-PRINTED POLYLACTIC ACID (PLA) POLYMER CHAINS: DESIGN, SIMULATION, AND MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Owing to the advancement of Additive Manufacturing (AM) technologies beside subtractive manufacturing, 3D printing processes have become a useful solution to address the present manufacturing techniques for industry viable products. This study presents the effect of tensile mechanical properties of chain links used for drive mechanism designed with polylactic acid (PLA) polymer using 3D printing. The specimen has been prepared using low nozzle infill rate, low layer resolution, and standard build speed and 220°C extrusion temperature using 3D printer. The three chain link model was designed in Autodesk Fusion 360 and the effects of tensile property using stress tool to calculate failure load under static tensile load of 1000 N was analysed after simulation in ANSYS considering five key parameters namely Equivalent Elastic Strain, Total Deformation, Equivalent von-Mises Stress, Shear Stress, and Maximum Principal Stress. The PLA chain links demonstrated its capability to withstand at adequate load application with performance metrics indicating tensile strength and stress distribution suitable for various technical aspects. However, prolonged distribution in deformation and failure thresholds highlight variations in material resilience. The simulation results confirmed that PLA polymer exhibits sufficient mechanical stability demonstrating failure load of 769.91 N, bridging the gap between lightweight design and manufacturing efficiency. This research emphasizes the feasibility of utilizing 3D-printed PLA chains as alternative product for industry.

Keywords: PLA 3D Printing, tensile properties, Simulation

1. INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic polymer materials have revolutionized modern industries by enhancing machine efficiency while reducing fuel consumption, cost, and overall weight [1]. Among various fabrication techniques, injection moulding is widely recognized for producing over 30% of thermoplastic components due to its precision, high yield, and automation capabilities [2][3]. Injection-moulded plastic parts, including chain links, are widely used for its low-weight, non-corrosive nature, moderate durability, availability and also for its low cost. Traditionally, metallic chains, though robust, are heavy and expensive to manufacture, required to shift towards polymer-based alternatives.

In the context of chain design, this research explores the use of 3D-printed chains fabricated with Nature Works Ingeo 4043D PLA, a renewable thermoplastic, under a tensile force of 1000 N [4]. The adoption of PLA offers distinct advantages, including sustainability and flexibility in manufacturing complex geometries using additive manufacturing.

This study aims to manufacture a PLA chain and analyse the mechanical properties focusing on their tensile strength and deformation behaviour under moderate loads and compare it with the same properties of Polypropylene polymer using ANSYS. Considering the load bearing capacity this polymer shows potential to replace traditional materials in applications such as conveyor belts, tool changers in CNC machine, and timing chains etc. Nowadays, polymer chains are used in food processing plant for water treatment and gas separation due to their good filtration properties which is helpful in manufacturing smart materials, sensors, and biotech innovations [9]. Polyester recycling makes industries eco-friendlier [11]. The Nanotechnology assisted with polymers improves batteries, electronics, and drug delivery [10].

The focus of present industries is to manufacture lightweight, low-cost, and eco-friendly materials. Metal chains are strong but are costly and heavy, so poly lactic acid, which is a biodegradable plastic, can be a better choice in this segment. This research work focused on the 3D printing of PLA chain and to observe

the strength and rate of deformation and also to compare with the data of Polypropylene (PP) from our analysis. This analysis helps to identify the affectivity of PLA chains for industrial product.

2. PRODUCT DESIGN

The 3D-printed chain link is designed based on the 12B series roller chain specifications, with a pitch of 19.05 mm, transverse pitch of 19.46 mm, roller diameter of 12.07 mm, and width of 11.68 mm (Table 1). Figure 1(a) presents its detailed dimensional drawing, ensuring compatibility with 12B standards, while Figure 1(b) shows the 3D model created in Autodesk Fusion 360 for additive manufacturing. The plastic link balances structural integrity and manufacturing feasibility for practical applications.

Table 1. 12B series simple roller chain standard dimensions [4]

Chain Parts	Simple Roller Chain 12B Series(mm)
Pitch	19.05
Transverse Pitch	19.46
Roller Diameter	12.07
Width	11.68

Figure 1. (a) Design of the polymer link with dimensions; (b) 3D model of the chain

2.1 Product Specification

INGEOTM 4043D (PLA) was selected for its structural performance, manufacturability, and sustainability. Following is the comparative properties of the two materials under observation (Table 2).

Table 2. Materials and Product Specifications [5][6]

Property	INGEOTM 4043D (PLA)	SABIC® PP 579S (Polypropylene Homopolymer)
Material Type	Biodegradable polymer	Polypropylene homopolymer
Density	1.24 g/cm ³	0.905 g/cm ³
Melt Flow Index (MFI)	6 g/10 min (190°C, 2.16 kg)	20 g/10 min (230°C, 2.16 kg)
Tensile Strength	60 MPa	High rigidity (1,800 MPa tensile modulus)
Melting/Glass Transition Point	55–60°C	100°C

2.2 Finite Element Method (FEM)

FEM is a numerical technique for solving complex engineering problems involving intricate geometries, boundary conditions, and material properties.

General Procedure

1. **Pre-processing:** Define the geometry, element types, material and geometric properties, meshing, boundary conditions, and loads. Evaluate stress, strain, deformation, and strain energy.
2. **Solution:** Solve governing equations using numerical techniques to compute fundamental variables and derive additional parameters.
3. **Post-processing:** Analyze results for stress distribution, strain, deformation, and strain energy.

2.3 Governing Equations

From a mathematical standpoint, the **Finite Element Method (FEM)** is used for solving a set of related differential equations. The **global FEM equation** is given as:

$$[F]=[K][U]$$

where:

- [F] represents the nodal forces.
- [U] represents the nodal displacements.
- [K] is the global stiffness matrix.

For **linear analysis stress**, Hooke's law is used:

$$\sigma=E\varepsilon$$

For **nonlinear analysis**, Finite Element Analysis (FEA) simulates shear, tension, and bending stresses using complex equations and empirical data.

The **strain energy** stored in a material due to deformation is calculated as:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int V \sigma \varepsilon dV$$

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

In this study, the mechanical behavior of the INGENO 4043D/PLA polymer has been investigated under varying failure loads. The material performance was analyzed based on five key mechanical parameters: Equivalent Elastic Strain, Total Deformation, Equivalent von-Mises Stress, Shear Stress, and Maximum Principal Stress. These parameters offer insights into how PLA polymer responds to different applied loads, deformation, and stress distribution. The findings from this comparative analysis help in understanding the suitability of these materials for various applications, especially in scenarios where material strength, flexibility, and durability are critical. The simulated data set is given in Table (3). It is found that PLA is stronger and more rigid than PP, with less deformation (0.32013 mm) and higher stress resistance (42.544 MPa von-Mises stress). PLA can handle adequate load (769.91 N) before breaking, thereby making it a good choice for conveyor belts, robotic tool changers, and other industrial uses. Due to its strong bonds and stiffness, PLA is a good alternative to traditional materials, giving them both strength and sustainability.

Table 3. Simulated data set of INGENO 4043D/PLA & SABIC PP 579S

Parameters	INGENO 4043D/PLA+		SABIC PP 579S	
	Failure Load - 769.91 N		Failure Load - 455.63 N	
	Min	Max	Min	Max
Equivalent Elastic Strain (mm/mm)	3.1945*10 ⁻⁴	14.862	3.6335*10 ⁻⁴	16.599

Total Deformation (mm)	0	0.32013	0	0.3696
Equivalent von-Mises Stress (MPa)	6.5019×10^{-8}	42.544	2.8872×10^{-8}	23.037
Shear Stress (MPa)	3.3884×10^{-8}	24.542	1.5477×10^{-8}	113.878
Maximum Principal Stress (MPa)	-8.3061	60	-6.16886	37

3.1. Total deformation and Failure

Total deformation reflects the extent to which this polymer deforms with subjected to external force. Deformation of PLA observed as quite low with a value of 0.32013 mm (Fig.2(a)), lower than reported as Plastic PP exhibits intermediate deformation at 0.3696 mm (Fig.2(b)). So, PLA shows more rigidity and structural stability.

It has been observed that PLA demonstrates adequate resilience before failure at static tensile load of 769.91 N, indicating it can endure greater forces before breaking down. This makes INGENO 4043D/PLA a more suitable material for applications where higher load-bearing capacity is required.

Figure 2. (a) Total Deformation of Ingeo 4043D (b) Total Deformation of Polymer PP

3.2. Equivalent Elastic Strain

Elastic strain refers to the material's ability to deform under stress and then return to its original shape once the stress is removed. INGENO 4043D/PLA exhibits a lower maximum strain of 14.862mm/mm (Fig.(3a)), making it less prone to deformation under stress compared to the maximum strain of 16.599 mm/mm for polymer PP (Fig.(3b)). These results suggest that PLA is stiffer material, offering more resistance to strain.

Figure 3. (a) Equivalent Elastic Strain of Ingeo 4043D (b) Equivalent Elastic Strain of Plastic PP

3.3. Equivalent von-Mises Stress

The von-Mises stress is a theoretical yield criterion used to predict the onset of yielding in ductile materials. PLA demonstrates the highest maximum von-Mises stress at 42.544 MPa (fig. 4(a)), indicating it can handle higher stress level before yielding. In comparison, Polymer PP shows a lower value of 22.921 MPa (Fig. 4(b)). The higher von-Mises stress in PLA suggests that it is more suitable for applications requiring higher strength and durability under stress.

Figure 4. (a) Equivalent von-Mises Stress of Ingeo 4043D (b) Equivalent von-Mises Stress of Polymer PP

3.4. Shear Stress

Shear stress is a measure of how a material responds to forces that cause sliding between its internal planes. The maximum shear stress is observed in polymer PLA at 24.542 MPa (fig. 5(a)), which is significantly higher than that of other polymer PLASTIC PP at 13.232 MPa (fig. 5(b)). This indicates that PLA is more resistant to shearing forces, making it a better option for applications where such forces are predominant.

Figure 5. (a) Shear Stress of Ingeo 4043D (b) Shear Stress of Polymer PP

3.5. Maximum Principal Stress

Maximum principal stress is the largest normal stress at a point, indicating the likelihood of material failure. Polymer PLA demonstrates the highest maximum principal stress at 60 MPa (Fig.6(a)), while polymer PP exhibits a lower value of 34.599 MPa (Fig. 6(b)). The high maximum principal stress for PLA implies that it can endure greater stress concentrations without failing, reinforcing its role as a high-performance material in cutting edge technologies.

Figure 6. (a) Maximum Principal Stress of PLA polymer (b) Maximum Principal Stress of Polymer PP

4. CONCLUSIONS

The PLA polymer three chain link has been designed and its mechanical properties simulation data of the 3D printed chain link of tensile mechanical properties namely Equivalent Elastic Strain, Total Deformation, Equivalent von-Mises Stress, Shear Stress, and Maximum Principal Stress. The simulated data analysed using stress tool and calculating factor of safety (F.O.S) in ANSYS to determine failure load of 769.91 N of the designed link. Hence, it has been ascertained the usefulness of PLA polymer even at adequate load application. The simulation results of Equivalent Elastic Strain of 14.862 mm/mm, Total Deformation of 420.320 mm, equivalent von-Mises Stress of 13.544 MPa, Shear Stress of 24.542 MPa, and Maximum Principal Stress of 60 MPa confirmed that PLA plastic possesses useful material properties

which make it a suitable material for industry. This research emphasizes the feasibility of utilizing 3D-printed polylactic acid polymer chains as alternative product.

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